

THE IMPORTANCE OF PERSONNEL IN INNOVATIVE ACTIVITY MANAGEMENT OF THE ENTERPRISE

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Abstract. The article evaluates the importance of personnel in the management of the innovative activity of the enterprise and the development indicators of the innovative management of the enterprise. Also, the organizational and economic mechanism of implementing innovative management in enterprises was analyzed, its specific features and existing problems were identified. In the long-term perspective, scientific proposals and practical recommendations have been developed regarding the possibilities of creative use of advanced foreign experience in improving the efficiency of innovative management of our country's personnel.

Keywords: innovation, management, innovative management, innovative activity, innovative specialization, modernization, personnel management.

As the processes of modernization of the economy continue in our country, changes will occur in all its links and lead to the establishment of a new economy. The implementation of innovative reforms in our republic will serve to improve the social lifestyle of the population, as well as the prosperous life of the people and the modern development of producers and service providers.

As a result, it leads to the innovative development of enterprise management based on the organization of new production in enterprises based on modern technologies, offering additional types of services, improving the quality of existing products and services.

Analyzes show that 80-95 percent of the additional growth of the gross domestic product in industrialized countries is due to the contribution of new knowledge based on innovation [1].

Innovation is the introduction of a new product or service to the market, the implementation of new production processes, the promotion of products or services, new forms of production organization or types of activities, the creation of new markets or the acquisition of a large share of the current market and existing markets by the new process. are directed efforts [2].

The concept of innovation in enterprises should be taken into account first of all, advanced ideas and developments. And scientific and technical achievements, technology and new inventions can also be expressed in the definition of innovation. According to M.Q.Pardaev, innovation refers to the use

of the results of developments based on advanced ideas as scientific and technical achievements, advanced technology and new inventions in various fields (in our economic, social, spiritual life, management system, etc.) a related phenomenon is understood [3].

In order for each country in the world to grow its innovative economy, its existing internal and external conditions, including social, economic conditions, production, industry, scientific and technical potential and other factors are taken into account. In the republic, large-scale works are being carried out in connection with innovative activities and are being involved in networks. At this point, the Law of the Republic of Uzbekistan on "Innovative Activities" was adopted in connection with the development of innovative activities in the Republic of Uzbekistan [4].

- This law defines the measures to support the training, retraining and improvement of the qualifications of personnel in the field of innovative activities:

- formation of state orders for personnel training in the field of innovative activity;

- development of state requirements and standards for training, retraining and upgrading of personnel in the field of innovative activity;

- to increase the activity of non-governmental educational organizations, vocational training centers that carry out personnel training, retraining and improvement of their qualifications in the field of innovative activity;

- promotion of science and technology achievements; supporting the technical creativity of young people and helping them by directing them to the profession.

- Otherwise, in chapter 4 of the decree of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan "On the approval of the innovative development strategy of the Republic of Uzbekistan in 2022-2026" "Innovative activity through the development of creativity, innovative entrepreneurship and rationalization skills at all stages of education" the following measures were determined in the direction of further development of human capital in management:

- to increase the role of students in innovative activities by forming the initial scientific, terminological, technological concepts of innovation;

- to create attractive incentive mechanisms and an environment of intellectual competition for young people entering science and innovative activities, intern-researchers and basic doctoral students to demonstrate their talents and rationalizing abilities in order to increase their knowledge and

level;

- to support the scientific and innovative activity of young people by further developing the activities of the Youth Academy, which includes talented schoolchildren and students;

- wide introduction of programs for acceleration of start-up projects in innovation centers, technology parks and regional innovation centers and business incubators in higher education organizations;

- training highly qualified personnel in the direction of innovation and technological activity management and organizing their regular scientific and practical internships; [5].

The formation and management of personnel in the innovative field creates the need to systematize modern thinking, to achieve the effectiveness of the creativity of the human mind, and to have foresight. Such an approach ensures the democratization and humanization of the innovation system, and serves to increase the level of quality. Identification of personnel group (segments). Innovative goals can be achieved through personnel policy:

- Management can be divided into social, potential, initial and final categories according to the level of clarification of the requirements for the personnel reserve in the innovative field. The social reserve of personnel is a broad concept. In this case, all labor resources are used (external and internal opportunities) and the foundation of the future personnel supply of the organization is created;

- it is understood that the potential reserve meets the main requirements for the level of education and specialization of managers, specialists, workers or in the near future if other parameters are taken into account.

A personal reserve should be formed in each department of the organization;

- initial reserve - this is the number of potential reserve employees, who have a high probability of being appointed to a leadership position;

- only working employees who almost fully meet all criteria are included in the final reserve.

In the formation of personnel in the innovative field, it is necessary to pay attention to the following:

- determining the knowledge of the need (ability);

- recruitment of personnel;

- efficient use of personnel;

- development of personnel (qualification improvement and retraining);

- organization of personnel information;
- personnel replacement (dismissal);
- formation of personnel reserves and their stimulation;
- it is necessary to pay attention to those who are in tune in the formation of personnel in the innovative field.

The strategy of personnel formation in innovation:

- personnel strategy;
- open (the enterprise is filled with innovative content from external sources);
- closed (focused on replenishing the innovative content of the enterprise from internal sources);
- planning;
- enterprise structure;
- staff table;
- reserve.

Innovative approaches to personnel management, along with technological innovations, help to increase labor productivity and the effectiveness of the organization as a whole. The introduction of management innovations in the field of labor allows influencing the motivational attitude of personnel towards the organization, influencing the choice of the most modern flexible methods and technologies for working with people. Innovative methods and technologies used in modern organizations help maintain a high level of labor discipline, increase the level of people's involvement, ensure the formation of a culture of communication within the organization and in the external environment, and provide an opportunity to manage one's own brand. In the process of implementing innovative personnel management, it is important to consider and rely on the following basic rules:

- 1) the need for strong interactions between the organization's development strategy and the human resource management strategy;
- 2) assessment of the level of impact of costs related to human resources management on the economic indicators of the organization;
- 3) formation of professional skills and competences of employees in the necessary amount for the effective functioning of the organization in the labor market..

Foydalanilgan adabiyotlar:

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